

Components' and Materials' Performance for Advanced Solar Supercritical CO₂ Powerplants

Informative Paper 1

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**DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF NEW PARTICLES FOR HIGH-
TEMPERATURE CONCENTRATING SOLAR RECEIVERS: STATE OF THE
ART AND INNOVATION BROUGHT BY COMPAS_sCO₂**

INTRODUCTION

One of the main challenges in the concentrating solar power (CSP) research community is related to the development of systems that can reach very high operating temperatures (in the order of 1000°C). High heat transfer medium temperatures allow the connection of solar energy into efficient innovative systems such as “solar fuels”¹, material production, solar water treatment, sea water desalination and synthesis of chemicals. COMPASsCO₂ project investigates the feasibility of using solid particles as both heat transfer and thermal storage media, thus reducing the complexity and costs of CSP power plants.

Currently, one main bottleneck lays in the selection of materials that can withstand high temperatures and are abrasion-resistant. The contribution of COMPASsCO₂ to this research stream is its focus on material and lifetime aspects of the particles and the metals being in contact with them, and the validation in a particle/s-CO₂ heat exchanger².

This article is a first of a series of informative papers aiming at disseminating the main achievements of COMPASsCO₂ project to a wide audience, in order to increase awareness on sustainable energy technologies and highlight the efforts of both research and industry for the transition to a carbon neutral energy mix in Europe. It summarises the activities conducted in the first 18 months of implementation (November 2020 - April 2022), and the main accomplishments, with a specific focus on the development and testing of novel materials.

STATE-OF-THE-ART

Among the various CSP technologies, central tower plants using molten salts as the working fluid have been selected as the business case in COMPASsCO₂ for their higher efficiency compared to linear systems. Nevertheless, the usable temperature range of molten salt is limited between 290°C and 565°C due to its freezing and decomposition behaviour.

Solid particle systems are considered as very promising option for future CSP systems because of their potential to reach higher temperatures and a considerable cost reduction compared to molten salts. The direct absorption principle in the receiver, where the concentrated solar radiation is directly absorbed by the dark solid particles, significantly reduces the need for high-temperature alloys and high absorptance coatings in the receiver (which has important durability issues) and ensures high receiver efficiency.

Currently, spherical sintered bauxite particles are used as hydraulic fracturing proppants in the oil and gas industry, and have also been evaluated for use in a direct absorption falling particle receiver in the CSP industry. One of the observed drawbacks of state-of-the-art bauxite particles is the reduction of their solar absorptance over time. The research and industrial challenge is to develop new particles with low cost, high heat capacity, high solar absorptance and minimum optical ageing over time.

COMPAS_sCO₂ CONTRIBUTION

In order to characterize particles, assess their performance, tune their properties to meet the requirements of thermal stability, high absorptance and abrasion resistance, and understand

¹ A solar fuel is a synthetic chemical fuel produced from solar energy. A solar fuel can be produced and stored for later use, when sunlight is not available, making it an alternative to fossil fuels and batteries. Examples of such fuels are hydrogen, ammonia, and hydrazine.

² Supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycles are more efficient power conversion systems than conventional Rankine cycles and their deployment is enabled by the higher temperature operation achieved in particles systems, beyond the limits of conventional salt-based receivers. The CSP s-CO₂ cycle considered in COMPASsCO₂ is a recompression Brayton cycle.

and model their lifetime, seven different types of particles are being tested within the framework of COMPASsCO₂ project. They include both state-of-the-art (Ultraprop Sintered Bauxite, Interprop and BauxLite) and two novel compositions (granulated and fused), all developed by Saint Gobain. In addition, three coatings on a selected substrate (chemical deposition coating by CIEMAT³, pigment coating in Resonance Acoustic Mixer by DLR⁴ and pack cementation coating by DECHEMA⁵) are being evaluated.

The state-of-the-art proppants investigated in COMPASsCO₂ are composed mostly of alumina, silica and iron oxide. Newly developed particles include granulated and fused particles. Granulated particles are produced using recycled iron oxide from steel industry. They present good stability regarding aging at high temperature and have a homogeneous microstructure. Fused particles are also produced through a high portion of recycled materials; they exhibit mainly Mg-spinel phases with varying Al, Si and Fe oxides. They have a very spherical and smooth surface, dense and dendritic structure, and present high solar absorptance.

In the selection of particles, the trade-off is between their performance and their overall sustainability profile. In particular, a key aspect to be considered is their cost, which is largely dependent on: i) the price volatility of the secondary raw material utilised; ii) the use in CSP with large particle size distribution; iii) the CSP industry annual demand and iv) the profitability of the manufacturing plants. One of the aims of COMPASsCO₂ is to develop highly efficient and durable particles for CSP receivers at a cost lower than 1 Euro per kg.

The targeted properties in COMPASsCO₂ are summarised in Figure 1.

Property category	Targets for receiver
Cost	<1€/kg for particles with $c_p < 1.2 \text{ J/g-K}$
LCOE	At least same LCOE as bauxite particles
Heat capacity	$C_p \geq 1.5 \text{ J/g-K}$ between 480-900°C (only if cost is acceptable), otherwise $> 1.2 \text{ J/g-K}$
Density	$> 2 \text{ g/cm}^3$ (bulk); $> 3.5 \sim 4 \text{ g/cm}^3$ (material)
Max. operational temperature	Sintering- (viscous flow temperature) $> 1000^\circ\text{C}$; Phase stability $> 900^\circ\text{C}$
Wear/ attrition resistance	mass loss by attrition $< 0.5 \text{ kg/MWh}_{\text{th,transferred}}$ (9000 impacts at 6.7m/s among particles expected)
Hardness	900-1100 (Vickers) (same as bauxite reference)
Lifetime	> 25 years; $> 100,000$ operational hours; 1 cycle per day (> 9000 in total)
Shape	Sphericity (aspect ratio of maximum and minimum diameter) > 0.9 Roundness (sharpness of edges): as good as bauxite
Size	0.3 mm - 1.19 mm
Solar absorptance α	> 0.9 (even lower values acceptable in cavity receivers)
Thermal emittance	Tbd (low)
Thermal conductivity	Al_2O_3 ($> 25 \text{ W/m-K}$ at room temperature; $> 8 \text{ W/m-K}$ at $\approx 700^\circ\text{C}$)

Figure 1 : Particle property targets and degree of relevance (source: COMPASsCO₂ WP2 presentation, January 2022)

PARTICLE CHARACTERISATION AND OPTIMISATION

As summarised in Figure 2 new optimized particles (fused and granulated) exhibit a better crystallized microstructure with no or negligible amount of glassy phase, which results in higher

³ Two different routes have been followed: 1) application of black spinels prepared with metal salt solutions (Cu, Mn, Co), deposited on particles by dip coating deposition technique followed by a thermal treatment, and; 2) application of metal coatings (Ni) with electroless plating and thermal treatment.

⁴ Particle coating by Resonance Acoustic Mixing was performed on one of the BauxLite proppants (BL 16/30). Commercial pigment coating enhanced the long-term absorptance of BL 16/30. Next steps will be to perform coating process optimisation of other state-of-the-art proppants with different particle size.

⁵ Pack cementation coating was conducted to enrich particle surface with chromium in order to improve their properties for use in the heat exchanger environment, with a specific focus on long-term stability.

softening temperature with respect to state-of-art proppants. This difference is more pronounced in the case of fused generations.

New developments

Figure 2 : Particles characterisation (source: COMPASsCO₂ WP2 presentation, third project meeting, 4 February 2022. By: DLR, SGOB, CIEMAT and DECH)

Moreover, some surface microscopic investigations reveal the distinct surface properties of proppants and fused particles as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 : Comparison of BL 16/30 (left) and fused generation 1 (right) particles

Enhanced sphericity, and roundness were achieved for fused particles. Moreover, surface roughness is minimized with well crystallized structural units at the surface, which is promising for minimizing mass losses due to abrasion and preventing dust formation.

In terms of solar absorptance fused particles show very high values (>97% in the case of second-generation fused particles), as displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4 : Comparison of solar absorptance across the tested samples

To measure the effects of thermal ageing some samples for state-of-the-art and novel material were exposed in alumina crucibles in muffle furnace to 1000°C for 1500 h. Results indicate reduced ageing for fused particles and no degradation effect on granulated particles compared to state-of-the-art (Figure 5).

Figure 5 : Ageing at constant temperature of 1000°C (source: DLR, CIEMAT)

A further step consisted in testing abrasion resistance of coating layers. It was found that a 1200 °C sintering process improves the abrasion resistance of the spinel coating applied by the Acoustic Resonance Mixer. To further investigate this aspect, a high temperature abrasion set-up is currently under construction by DLR and CIEMAT at Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), Spain.

Table 1 compares novel particles and state-of-the-art proppants with respect to the properties that have been prioritized for the CSP application, as displayed in Figure 1. The green arrows indicate that the specific particle exceeds the defined targets, whereas the red ones mean that the particle underperforms. Blank spaces mean that no data has been collected yet. The table will be updated along the course of the project implementation to provide an overview of the different particle developments.

Table 1: Comparison of properties of state-of-the-art proppants and optimized particles

Property	Target values	Sintered Bauxite SB 30/50	BauxLite BL 16/30	BauxLite BL 30/50	InterProp IP 30/50	Granulated Gen 2	Fused Gen 1	Fused Gen 2	CIEMAT Coating on BL16/30	DLR coating on BL16/30
Size distribution [μm]		297-590	590-1190	297-590	297-590	600-1250	800-1200	600-1200	590-1190	590-1190
Cost [€/kg]	<1	↓	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓		
c_p at 1000°C [J/g·K]	>1.2	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑		
Bulk density ρ_b [g/cm ³]	>2	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑		
Material density ρ_m [g/cm ³] specific /absolute	>3.5	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓		
Softening temperature T_s [°C]	>900	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑		
Vickers Hardness $HV_{0.1}$	>900	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↑		
Breaking force F [N] 0.8-1.0mm	>140		↑			↓	↓	↓		
Sphericity [-] B/L (Q3=50.0%)	>0.9	↓	↓	↓	↓		↑			
Solar absorptance α [-]	>0.9	↓	↑	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Thermal emittance ϵ at 700°C [-]	<0.85	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↓		↑	

NEXT STEPS AND CONCLUSIONS

Four state-of-the-art proppant types have been extensively characterized in terms of phase composition, microstructure, optical properties, density, heat capacity, hardness and other properties. Two novel particle types have been developed and tested against the state of the art. One type is based on granulation using iron oxide waste products to remain at low cost. The other type is based on fusing metallic oxides at very high temperature. In addition, three types of coatings have been deposited on state-of-the-art proppants.

Preliminary results from chemical deposition coating indicate that absorptance is increased after applying one spinel layer and curing at 800°C for one hour. In the next steps, consecutive spinel layers will be deposited to check the effect of coating thickness on the optical properties and thermal durability at 1000°C. Regarding nickel coating, the deposition of nickel produced an increase of solar reflectance in the solar range which is dependent on the deposition time. A complete characterisation of nickel coated particles will be performed in the next months. Additional tests by RAM and pack cementation are ongoing on other state-of-the-art proppants with different particle size.

Granulated particles exhibit improved optical performance, higher optical durability at 1,000°C, higher density, higher softening temperature compared to the state of the art. Hardness and breaking force remain to be improved.

Fused particles achieve excellent solar absorptance beyond 97% and excellent hardness but their cost is higher compared to the state of the art. Coated proppants achieved up to 11% higher absorptance compared to the state-of-the-art proppant. Optical durability and attrition resistance of the coatings remain to be evaluated.

Several additional tests will be performed at laboratory scale to evaluate the performance of the different particles. In particular, the degradation mechanisms due to high temperature oxidation combined with erosion and high temperature corrosion issued from s-CO₂ will be analysed. Modelling work will be performed using the experimental results. The work aims at modelling the degradation progress with time in long term perspective, and to estimate the lifetime of the new materials and coatings under different conditions.

The project COMPASsCO₂ opens the path for a future commercial application of solar s-CO₂ Brayton cycle with the development of novel materials and components specifically designed for the linkage of the solar/storage system with power cycle via a particles / s-CO₂ heat exchanger. This requires the joint research effort of CSP and material researchers as well and industrial components manufacturer specialists.

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PUBLICATION CREDIT

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ABOUT COMPAS_sCO₂

COMPAS_sCO₂ aims to integrate CSP particle systems into highly efficient s-CO₂ Brayton power cycles for electricity production. Its research focus is on three main technological improvements:

- **development of new particles**

In order for particles to meet high temperatures new ceramic particles with improved performance will be developed and tested under relevant conditions

- **development of new metal alloys**

Answers about how the processing and combination with substrate steels will affect the microstructure, phase composition and also chemical stability of the newly developed materials will be provided. Modelling the degradation progress over time to estimate the lifetime of the new materials and coatings under different conditions will be performed.

- **development of the heat exchanger section**

To validate the interaction between the developed particles and the new structural materials in a relevant environment, the project includes the design, construction and testing of a heat exchanger section. Parameters relevant for the lifetime, like attrition rates, and performance parameters, like heat transfer, on the tube and first operating experiences are generated in a relevant heat exchanger environment.

In addition to the research component, COMPAS_sCO₂ includes a **communication and dissemination package for a wide range of stakeholders**. This Horizon 2020 project has a four-year duration (2020-2024) and is coordinated by DLR, with 12 European partners.

For more information

Check the project's website: www.compassco2.eu

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